

A targeted NanoString analysis of immune gene expression in smokers and non-smokers with severe periodontitis

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Abstract

Objectives: Periodontitis is a chronic inflammatory disease whose severity is strongly influenced by environmental factors, particularly smoking. Smoking is a well-established risk factor for both the onset and progression of periodontitis, contributing to impaired immune responses, delayed healing, and enhanced tissue destruction. In this pilot study, we explored differences in immune-related gene expression between smokers and non-smokers with severe periodontitis.

Methods: Gene expression analysis was performed on RNA isolated from saliva samples of six smokers and four non-smokers with severe periodontitis using a targeted NanoString panel comprising 249 immune-related genes.

Results: Comparative analysis revealed a distinct expression pattern in smokers, with significantly higher expression of several pro-inflammatory genes, including *IL1A*, *CCL3*, *CCL4*, and *IL8*. These genes are involved in leukocyte recruitment, chemotaxis, and inflammatory signaling.

Conclusion: Although limited by the small sample size, these findings suggest an association between smoking and an enhanced inflammatory gene expression profile in patients with severe periodontitis. The results should be interpreted as exploratory, providing preliminary molecular insights into the way tobacco exposure modulates immune responses in periodontal disease.

Keywords

differentially expressed genes (DEGs), immune gene expression, inflammation, NanoString technology, severe periodontitis, smoking

Introduction

Periodontitis remains a major global public health challenge. According to a recent study published in 2025, there were approximately 951 million prevalent cases of periodontal diseases worldwide in 2021, corresponding to an age-standardized prevalence rate of 17 per 100,000 persons (Fu et al. 2025). These statistics underline the high

burden of periodontitis worldwide and highlight the urgent need for effective public health interventions.

Well-established risk factors for the disease include poor oral hygiene and inadequate plaque control, systemic conditions such as diabetes mellitus, genetic susceptibility, advanced age, stress, and certain medications that affect gingival tissues (Frencken et al. 2017). In addition to environmental determinants, dysregulation of the

immune system is also a crucial factor in periodontitis incidence, including the magnitude of the host inflammatory response and the presence of polymorphisms in pro-inflammatory genes (Kozak et al. 2020). Epidemiological studies have demonstrated that smokers are at a significantly increased risk of developing periodontitis compared to non-smokers. A meta-analysis reported that smokers demonstrate an 85% higher risk of developing the disease (Leite et al. 2018). A survey published in 2000 showed that current smokers are about four times more likely to develop periodontitis compared to non-smokers after adjusting for age, gender, race/ethnicity, education, and income-to-poverty ratio (Tomar and Asma 2000). Thus, the authors concluded that smoking may be responsible for more than half of periodontitis cases among adults in the United States (Tomar and Asma 2000).

Data on gene expression in periodontitis, specifically differentially expressed genes in smokers versus non-smokers, remain limited. A recent study published in 2025 reported gene expression changes in human gingival tissues induced by smoking (Zhang et al. 2025). Single-cell transcriptomics revealed overexpression of genes associated with wound healing (*COMP*, *IGFBP2*), chemotaxis (e.g., *CXCL14*, *HSPB1*, *S100A14*), and aging (e.g., *CXCL14*, *HSPB1*, *S100A14*). Analysis of cell-to-cell communication and immune cells in smokers revealed upregulation of *CXCL12*, linking macrophages to *CXCR4*. Furthermore, the authors showed that targeting *CXCL12* decreased inflammation and bone resorption in individuals who smoke (Zhang et al. 2025).

Our study builds upon previous transcriptomic analyses by further examining immune-related gene expression differences between smokers and non-smokers. Unlike conventional RNA-to-cDNA-based approaches, we applied an amplification-free NanoString platform, which reduced amplification-associated technical variability in gene expression quantification. Moreover, by focusing specifically on immune-associated genes, our study provides a more targeted insight into immune-related pathways involved in periodontitis.

Materials and methods

Participants, sample collection, and RNA isolation

Participants in this study provided written informed consent for voluntary participation in the research project. Ethical approval was issued by the Ethical Commission of the Medical University – Sofia (No. 2420/23.05.2024). All participants were between 18 and 70 years of age and were diagnosed with severe periodontitis stage III/IV by experts at the Department of Periodontology, Faculty of Dental Medicine, Medical University – Sofia. Classification was performed according to criteria established by the American Academy of Periodontology (AAP) and the

European Federation of Periodontology (EFP) (Tonetti et al. 2018). Excluded individuals were those who (1) used anti-inflammatory or immunosuppressive drugs in the past 6 months prior to biological sample collection; (2) used antibiotics in the past 6 months prior to sample collection; or (3) were pregnant or breastfeeding.

Total RNA was isolated from each saliva sample using the Quick-RNA Miniprep Plus Kit (Zymo, CA, US). Before isolation, saliva samples were stored in buffer for up to one week using RNA/DNA Shield (Zymo, CA, US). RNA quality and concentration were assessed by measuring concentration in ng/μl using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific), as well as by estimating protein and chemical contamination through absorbance ratios (A260/A280 and A260/A230).

NanoString gene expression analysis

Gene expression profiling was performed using the nCounter® Human Inflammation Panel (NanoString Technologies, Seattle, WA, USA), which directly quantifies mRNA transcripts without the need for enzymatic amplification. This panel targets 249 immune-related human genes and six reference control genes (*CLTC*, *GAPDH*, *GUSB*, *HPRT1*, *PGK1*, and *TUBB*), allowing focused analysis of inflammatory and immune pathways.

A total of 20 ng of RNA from each sample was hybridized to reporter and capture probe sets according to the manufacturer's protocol. Hybridized samples were processed on the nCounter® Prep Station and scanned using the Digital Analyzer. Raw counts were subjected to quality control and normalization using nSolver™ Analysis Software, version 4.0 (NanoString Technologies), with background correction based on negative controls and normalization to the included housekeeping genes.

Genes with mean normalized counts below 20 across all samples were excluded to minimize the influence of low-abundance transcripts, yielding a dataset comprising 99 genes for further analysis.

Statistical analysis

Fold changes were calculated as the ratio of mean gene expression in smokers versus non-smokers. To focus the analysis on biologically meaningful expression differences, genes exhibiting a fold change greater than two (FC > 2) were selected *a priori* for statistical evaluation.

Differential gene expression between smokers and non-smokers was assessed for this restricted gene set using the Welch *t*-test performed in R (version 4.5.1), and raw *p*-values were calculated for each gene. To account for multiple testing within this gene subset, *p*-values were adjusted using the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction method.

Descriptive statistics were obtained for the analyzed genes (Table 1), and visualization of expression differences between groups was performed using box plots (Fig. 1).

Table 1. Genes exhibiting a fold change greater than two ($FC > 2$) between smokers ($n = 6$) and non-smokers ($n = 4$) with severe periodontitis.

Gene symbol	Gene name	Transcript number	Smokers Mean \pm SD	Non-smokers Mean \pm SD	Fold change in smokers vs. non-smokers	<i>p</i> -value	FDR value
IL1A	Interleukin-1 alpha	NM_000575.3	64.43 \pm 25.38	26.74 \pm 12.59	2.41	0.02	0.08
CCL4	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligands 4	NM_002984.2	153.39 \pm 70.65	57.71 \pm 41.85	2.66	0.03	0.08
IL8	Interleukin-8	NM_000584.2	13982.81 \pm 7555.99	6731.74 \pm 1845.68	2.08	0.04	0.08
CCL3	Chemokine (C-C motif) ligands 3	NM_002983.2	179.09 \pm 146.53	55.97 \pm 51.60	3.20	0.04	0.08
HLA-DRB1	Major histocompatibility complex, class II, DR beta 1	NM_002124.1	134.51 \pm 72.95	59.20 \pm 46.68	2.27	0.06	0.08
CXCL2	C-X-C motif chemokine ligand 2	NM_002089.3	136.21 \pm 95.67	58.99 \pm 22.61	2.31	0.07	0.08
HLA-DRA	Major histocompatibility complex, class II, DR alpha	NM_019111.3	220.17 \pm 142.25	79.33 \pm 109.44	2.78	0.07	0.08
HSPB1	Heat shock protein beta-1	NM_001540.3	71.58 \pm 279.27	33.45 \pm 40.73	2.14	0.44	0.44

Figure 1. Box plot analysis of the top upregulated genes between smokers (S) and non-smokers (NS) with severe periodontitis, generated using NanoString® nSolver™ Analysis Software (version 4.0). **A.** *CCL3*; **B.** *CCL4*; **C.** *IL1A*; **D.** *IL8* expression levels in non-smokers and smokers.

Results

In this study, gene expression profiling was performed using the NanoString® Human Inflammation Panel in six smokers and four non-smokers of Bulgarian origin with severe periodontitis. After quality control and elimination of low-expression signals (less than 20 digital counts across all samples), a total of 99 genes showed expression differences between the two analyzed groups.

Following normalization and expression-based filtering, genes exhibiting a biologically meaningful fold change greater than two ($FC > 2$) between smokers and non-smokers were selected for further statistical evalua-

tion. Eight genes met these criteria and are summarized in Table 1.

Among these genes, four (*IL1A*, *CCL4*, *IL8*, and *CCL3*) showed higher expression levels in smokers, with nominal *p*-values < 0.05 . Four additional genes (*HLA-DRB1*, *CXCL2*, *HLA-DRA*, and *HSPB1*) exhibited fold changes greater than two but did not reach nominal statistical significance.

After adjustment for multiple testing using the Benjamini–Hochberg false discovery rate (FDR) correction applied within this gene subset, none of the analyzed genes reached statistical significance at an FDR threshold of < 0.05 ; the lowest FDR-adjusted *p*-value observed was 0.08.

The genes showing the largest expression differences in smokers included pro-inflammatory cytokines and chemokines (*IL1A*, *IL8*, *CCL3*, *CCL4*, and *CXCL2*), as well as genes involved in antigen presentation (*HLA-DRB1* and *HLA-DRA*) and cellular stress responses (*HSPB1*).

The box plots illustrate the expression levels of the four genes showing the largest fold changes (*IL1A*, *IL8*, *CCL3*, and *CCL4*) in smokers vs. non-smokers with severe periodontitis. Higher median expression levels for these genes were observed in smokers compared to non-smokers, despite variability among individual samples (Fig. 1). These plots highlight expression differences observed within this cohort for selected inflammation- and chemokine-related genes and support the exploratory findings derived from the statistical analysis.

To evaluate the functional and physical interactions among the four genes with nominal *p*-values < 0.05 and an FDR of 0.08 – *IL1A* (FC = 2.41), *CCL4* (FC = 2.66), *IL8* (FC = 2.08), and *CCL3* (FC = 3.20) – a protein–protein interaction (PPI) network was generated using STRING v11.5 (<https://string-db.org>) (Fig. 2). This network is based on curated databases, literature mining, and predictive algorithms and does not represent interactions directly measured in the clinical samples analyzed in this study. While these observations highlight known biological relationships among these inflammatory mediators, the small number of input genes and the exploratory nature of the study preclude conclusions regarding coordinated regulation specific to smokers. The PPI network is therefore presented as supportive background, providing a framework for future functional validation studies.

Figure 2. Functional interaction network of upregulated immune genes with the highest FDR values in smokers with periodontitis. Nodes represent proteins encoded by these genes, and edges indicate known or predicted interactions based on experimental evidence and curated databases. Edge thickness represents interaction confidence scores, highlighting the coordinated upregulation of these inflammatory mediators in smokers.

Functional validation in larger cohorts and experimental models will be required to assess the biological relevance of these associations.

Discussion

The gene that showed the highest increase in expression in smokers with severe periodontitis was *CCL3* (fold change 3.20). It is a CC chemokine, also known as macrophage inflammatory protein 1-alpha (MIP-1-alpha). Secreted by a wide range of cells, including fibroblasts, epithelial cells, and lymphocytes, it binds to *CCR1*, *CCR4*, and *CCR5* receptors expressed on T cells, dendritic cells, B cells, and eosinophils (Bhavsar et al. 2015). *CCL3* is well recognized as a key inflammatory mediator and is frequently recruited to sites of inflammation. Its established role in inflammatory responses and osteoclast activation has led to its implication in periodontal tissue destruction, particularly in aggressive forms of periodontitis (Garlet et al. 2003).

Previous protein-based studies suggest that increased *CCL3* levels are associated with a higher risk of developing periodontitis and that *CCL3* may serve as a salivary marker of the disease (Al-Sabbagh et al. 2012). However, these findings primarily reflect protein expression and disease activity rather than transcriptional regulation. In the present study, we extend existing knowledge by demonstrating upregulation of *CCL3* mRNA in individual samples, specifically in smokers compared to non-smokers with severe periodontitis. These observations may reflect the influence of smoking on chemokine gene expression within periodontal tissues, although direct extrapolation between transcript levels, protein abundance, and clinical outcomes remains limited.

A similar expression pattern was observed for *CCL4* (fold change 2.66), another CC chemokine that shares receptor usage with *CCL3*, particularly *CCR5*, which is involved in monocyte and macrophage recruitment to inflammatory sites. Similar to *CCL3*, *CCL4* interacts with the *CCR5* receptor, and, in combination, these chemokines promote resorptive processes in periodontitis (Repeke et al. 2010). Some studies suggest that *CCL4* induces VEGF-C expression, which is directly linked to the development of oral squamous cell carcinoma (Lien et al. 2018). The upregulation of both chemokines in smokers may therefore reflect amplified leukocyte infiltration within inflamed periodontal tissues. Although *CCL3* and *CCL4* have been proposed as potential biomarkers in prior studies, these findings should be interpreted cautiously, as the limited sample size and absence of protein-level validation restrict conclusions largely to transcriptional differences rather than biomarker performance.

In addition to chemokines, *IL1A* and *IL8* also showed significantly elevated expression in this study (fold changes 2.41 and 2.08, respectively). Both genes encode potent pro-inflammatory cytokines involved in neutrophil activation and amplification of local inflammatory responses, reflecting enhanced innate immune activation in smokers.

Data regarding *IL1A* expression in relation to smoking in periodontitis remain limited (Wicaksono et al. 2017). In a study by Wicaksono et al., *IL1A* protein levels were measured using an ELISA assay, and no significant differences were reported between smokers vs. non-smokers with periodontitis. However, significant differences were observed among non-smokers with varying disease severity (Wicaksono et al. 2017).

Our observation of increased *IL1A* expression in smokers with severe periodontitis (Fig. 1) suggests that smoking may modulate inflammatory gene regulation at the transcriptional level. Further conclusions, such as enhanced tissue destruction, cannot be inferred without complementary protein expression data.

Similarly, elevated expression of *IL8* in smokers with periodontitis is supported by several previous studies (Nanakaly et al. 2020; Lutfioglu et al. 2016). *IL8* is a potent neutrophil chemoattractant and contributes to the release of proteolytic enzymes and reactive oxygen species, thereby accelerating tissue destruction in periodontitis. In smokers, increased *IL8* expression may perpetuate a pro-inflammatory microenvironment and impair tissue repair, resulting in reduced healing capacity following periodontal breakdown. Salivary *IL8* levels have been reported to be significantly higher in smokers with chronic periodontitis and are associated with worsened periodontal status compared to non-smokers (Nanakaly et al. 2020). Similarly, increased *IL8* levels in gingival crevicular fluid of smokers with varying periodontal conditions may reflect smoking-induced alterations in immune responses.

Smoking-associated upregulation of *HLA-DRB1* and *HLA-DRA* in periodontitis may be connected with enhanced antigen presentation activity and altered immune cell functions induced by smoking. Smoking is likely to impact the expression of MHC class II molecules by increasing their expression in inflammatory settings (Strzelak et al. 2018). Tobacco smoke also contains numerous pro-inflammatory components that activate NF- κ B and MAPK pathways, which in turn may promote the transcription of chemokines such as *CXCL2*, a neutrophil chemoattractant (Zhou et al. 2025).

In addition, the STRING network illustrates known associations among four prominently regulated genes in this study (*IL1A*, *CCL4*, *IL8*, and *CCL3*). Gene ontology enrichment highlights that these proteins are associated with positive regulation of leukocyte migration, cytokine activity, and cytokine receptor binding. Therefore, they may collectively contribute to pathological processes in smoking-associated periodontitis. Although this analysis highlights previously reported functional relationships, it remains exploratory and does not allow conclusions regarding coordinated regulation or smoking-specific effects.

Overall, our findings indicate that smoking and associated oxidative stress likely dysregulate normal immune gene expression, resulting in altered transcriptional profiles in smokers versus non-smokers with severe periodontitis. Future studies incorporating longitudinal designs, protein-level validation, and functional analyses

will be necessary to clarify the biological and clinical relevance of these transcriptomic changes.

Conclusion

In summary, using NanoString expression analysis, we identified differences in immune-related gene expression between smokers and non-smokers with periodontitis. Our results demonstrated higher expression of *CCL3*, *CCL4*, *IL8*, and *IL1A* in smokers. These findings highlight associations between smoking and altered chemokine and cytokine transcript profiles in periodontal tissues, suggesting pathways that may contribute to enhanced inflammation.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Medical University – Sofia, KENIMUS (ethical committee).

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

D. Nikolova performed the experiments, analyzed the data, and prepared the manuscript; D. Dimitrov collected the saliva samples and performed the statistical analysis; I. Dimova participated in the statistical analysis and suggested interpretations; and V. Dosseva-Panova established the clinical criteria for patient selection and critically revised the manuscript.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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